

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D8.4

Report of main achievements, impacts, sustainability and exploitation

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1. Executive Summary

The main objective of the CINECA project is to build a federated solution that enables population-scale genomic and biomolecular data to be accessible internationally, accelerating research and improving health. The necessary infrastructure for data acquisition and analysis for a single cohort is a well-understood task, but sustaining meta-analyses across similar cohorts is challenging. CINECA project has addressed these challenges by focusing on the 'Researcher Journey', the steps a researcher/clinician must take to find, access and analyze data stored in different locations while complying with ethical and legal requirements. In this deliverable we recap the results of the CINECA project; we report on the general achievements of the project, describe the individual outputs and their impact, and evaluate the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) established at the beginning of the project.

This deliverable will focus on CINECA's achievements and impact. Information about the project's strategy for long-term sustainability of CINECA's outputs are described in Deliverable D8.3 - Report of impact and key results¹.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has met the following objectives:

- a) To provide a comprehensive summary of the CINECA project's general achievements.
- b) To present an overview of the integration for the different developments performed by each CINECA Work Package (WP).
- c) To provide insight into the impact of the CINECA project.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Over the past four decades, there has been a remarkable increase in the availability of cohort datasets within the field of disease research. These healthcare datasets, originally created for the investigation of specific diseases, have now evolved into highly valuable resources with the potential to contribute to the knowledge of diverse health conditions. In addition, this increased number of available datasets generated worldwide has led to a significant change in the access of this data for research purposes. In the past, researchers primarily relied on a centralized system where they had to download data locally to analyze it. However, this approach has become impractical and inefficient

¹ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/deliverables>

due to the sheer amount of data being generated and increased jurisdictional restrictions for human genetic data.

To adapt to this evolving landscape, a more decentralized and federated approach has emerged. Instead of downloading and centralizing data from various healthcare organizations, researchers now have the opportunity to access and analyze data directly from its original location. This shift towards a federated system allows researchers to tap into vast datasets distributed across different healthcare organizations, eliminating the need for time-consuming data transfers. However, the utilization of this data presents notable obstacles owing to its sensitive character and dispersed storage across various countries and continents. The CINECA project aims to address the challenges a clinician/researcher would encounter when trying to re-use data stored in different locations, what we call the 'Researcher Journey' (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Summary of steps a researcher/clinician needs to take to find, access and analyze federated data, complying always with the corresponding ELSI framework².

First, the researcher/clinician needs to know where the data they are interested in is located (**Federated data discovery**). Once located, the data holding organization needs to evaluate the access request and, if approved, authorize requester's access to their data (**Data access**). Moreover, in order for the requester to perform analyses with data from different sources, this needs to be harmonized so that the same analysis workflow can be run in the different datasets (**Data harmonization**). Finally, the researcher/clinician needs to be able to run federated workflows in the different datasets for analysis (**Federated data analysis**) or diagnostic services (**Federated healthcare applications**). In addition, due to the sensitive nature of the healthcare data used in these studies, all these steps need to comply with national and international ethical and legal regulations (**ELSI framework**).

Within the CINECA project, tools have been created for each stage of the Researcher Journey to effectively overcome the challenges encountered at each step. In addition, training has been developed to upskill researchers' engagement with these steps. In this deliverable we summarize the project achievements, their impact and describe KPIs gathered during the CINECA project.

² Icons from <https://www.flaticon.com/>

3.2 Description of Work

3.2.1 CINECA main achievements

Federated data discovery

The first step in the ‘Researcher Journey’ is for the researcher/clinician to locate the data they are interested in. For this purpose, CINECA WP1 has created a “Federated Discovery Portal”, which includes different components:

- Beacon Network v2
CINECA has used GA4GH Beacon v2 Protocol³ as a discovery tool for genomic and phenoclinic data. During the project, 3 beacon endpoints⁴ have been created at EGA⁵, CSC⁶ and C3G⁷. EGA and CSC are currently part of the Beacon Network, and we expect C3G’s to be added soon. In addition, a 4th Beacon endpoint is under development at H3Africa⁸.
- Query Expansion Services
In order to locate the relevant dataset regardless of the ontology employed or the format/syntax utilized to describe the variants by the different Cohorts, CINECA has implemented a Query Expansion Service⁹ in the Beacon query, which expands the user’s search by using ontologies and a data driven approach, where search terms are expanded to similar concepts in other ontologies.
- Data Visualization Tools
A Federated Discovery Portal¹⁰ has been developed as a User Interface¹¹ (UI) to facilitate the user’s Beacon queries, which includes a search box to perform Beacon queries, the Query Expansion Services to improve the results obtained, and allows users to fine-tune several parameters to shape the desired response.

Data access

After locating the data the researcher must request access to the hosting facilities to analyze it. However, the process of requesting individual access to each organization possessing the data can pose a challenge, as distinct organizations may adhere to diverse access protocols. To overcome this issue, GA4GH has developed GA4GH Passports and Authorization & Authentication Infrastructure

³ <https://beacon-project.io/>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/8093973>

⁵ <https://ega-archive.org/test-beacon-apis/cineca>

⁶ <https://b1mg-beacon.rahtiapp.fi/api>

⁷ <https://bqc19.c3g.calculquebec.ca/api/beacon/>

⁸ https://beacon.h3abionet.org/h3a_wgs/info

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/4609335>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/8099693>

¹¹ <https://beacon-network-cineca-demo.ega-archive.org/>

(AAI) specifications¹² to standardize the process for requesting and accessing data across different jurisdictions. CINECA WP2 has worked on leveraging these tools in the CINECA workflows:

- AAI support of GA4GH passports
CINECA WP2 directly contributed to the Passport and AAI standards approved by the GA4GH in October 2019. Therefore, a first report providing an overview of GA4GH Passports and AAI standards was created¹³, which provided insight on how these technologies could be applied to the CINECA workflows.
- Cross-authentication and authorization between different infrastructures
In order to prove how to facilitate user data access among databases located in different jurisdictions, AAI was implemented in ELIXIR (Europe) and CanDIG (Canada) infrastructures¹⁴, which allowed for:
 - Cross infrastructure authentication and delivery of authorization information between ELIXIR and CanDIG using the same user login.
 - Flexibility in the workflow due to the possibility to distribute the “Data access” process steps among the organizations involved: *user authentication* can be performed at organization 1 (e.g. user home university), *authorisation* can be provided by organization 2 (e.g. the competent DAC), and *access control* can take place in organization 3 (e.g. the cloud where the data has been made available).
- Integration of new cohorts to AAI infrastructure
After the AAI integration of ELIXIR and CanDIG to enable interoperability (bridge AAI), WP2 studied how to integrate other cohort infrastructures into this bridge AAI¹⁵:
 - Work was done to migrate ELIXIR AAI to Lifescience AAI¹⁶, which integrated AAI access with services provided by 12 other life science research infrastructures.
 - WP2 studied possible solutions to different user scenarios regarding data access that could be applied afterwards to CINECA cohorts, based on the previous AAI bridging work done for ELIXIR AAI and CanDIG. These scenarios involved control access of biobanking data (e.g. using BBMRI Negotiator or the European Genomics Data Infrastructure), or integration of infrastructure projects to LifeScience AAI (e.g. for the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases or the European Federation for Cancer Images).

¹²

https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/ga4gh-passports-and-the-authorization-and-authentication-infrastructure

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/record/5795408>

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/3938916>

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/8056340>

¹⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/AAI-migration>

Data harmonization

To allow for human cohort data discovery and analysis across jurisdictions it is necessary to harmonize cohort data so that there is interoperability between the queried cohorts. CINECA WP3 has developed different tools for this purpose:

- Minimal Metadata Model (MME)
The MME was created by collecting and structuring key variables from the CINECA cohorts¹⁷. However, the distribution of this particular model was in the form of a spreadsheet, which served its purpose for human review, but was not machine-readable or compliant with the latest semantic standards.
- Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology (GECKO)
The MME was used as a base to create the GECKO¹⁸, a model ontology compliant with semantic standards used for consistent representation of cohort metadata. Combined with an Ontology Cross-references tool (OxO¹⁹) and an Ontology Annotation tool (ZOOMA²⁰), a harmonization pipeline²¹ has been created which has been successfully used in harmonizing CINECA cohorts, and in other projects like the International HundredK+ Cohort Consortium²² (IHCC), or the Davos Alzheimer's Collaborative (DAC) project²³.
- Text-mining pipeline
In addition, to expand in the harmonization possibilities, CINECA worked a method to extract standardized concepts from unstructured and partially structured fields present in the cohorts' data. Different text mining models²⁴ were analyzed for this purpose, which resulted in the development of the CINECA Text Mining Aggregate API²⁵, which is used to provide ontology terms from free text.
- Data Use Ontology (DUO) codes
Data Access Committees (DACs) need to review the access requests individually, which can delay the access process by months. CINECA has been involved in the development of Data Use Ontology²⁶ (DUO) codes, which is a GA4GH approved technical standard²⁷. Thanks to the work done in the CINECA project, these DUO codes have been already implemented in CINECA cohorts located in EGA or H3Africa²⁸.

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/4575460>

¹⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/gecko>

¹⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/spot/oxo/>

²⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/spot/zooma/>

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/5055308>

²² <https://ihccglobal.org/>

²³ <https://www.davosalzheimerscollaborative.org/>

²⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/5795433>

²⁵ <http://45.88.81.24:8080/>

²⁶ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

²⁷ https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/data-use-ontology-approved-as-a-ga4gh-technical-standard/

²⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/5795449>

- Synthetic Datasets

At the initial phases of the CINECA project developers faced the challenge of acquiring real-world data to test and refine their innovations, which entailed complicated and time-consuming data access procedures. To overcome this issue, 4 Synthetic Cohort Datasets were created based on CINECA Cohorts, which could be freely used by developers (they have no identifiable data) while providing identical outcomes to those obtained from real data (they contain the same characteristics and data fields as real human cohorts)²⁹:

- Synthetic Cohort Europe UK1
- Synthetic Cohort Europe CH SIB
- Synthetic Cohort Africa H3ABionet
- Synthetic Cohort NA Canada CHILD

Federated data analysis

Once the data has been discovered and accessed, the researcher needs to analyze it to perform their studies. CINECA WP4 has developed different pipelines that streamline federated genetic analysis of molecular traits across multiple international cohorts, thus alleviating the challenges associated with data transfer across jurisdictional boundaries. These pipelines bring together the outcomes of WP1, WP2 and WP3 regarding data discovery, access and harmonization, respectively, while adding new analysis tools as the last steps of the whole workflow.

CINECA WP4 has used Expression Quantitative Trait Loci (eQTL)³⁰ analyses as a Use Case, and has created 6 modular workflows to quantify and normalise molecular traits for eQTL studies.

- eQTL analysis Workflows

All the eQTL analysis workflows are written in Nextflow language, have been packed into publicly available Docker/Singularity containers, and come with small test datasets that simplify deployment. These workflows are modular, so that they can be combined to achieve different data analysis outcomes, and they are containerized, which facilitates their implementation in different types of infrastructures from different locations³¹.

These workflows cover:

- Gene expression and splicing quantification: eQTL-Catalogue/rnaseq³²
- Molecular trait normalisation and QC: eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm³³
- Genotype imputation and quality control: eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute³⁴
- cis-QTL association testing and fine mapping: eQTL-Catalogue/qtimap³⁵

²⁹ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/cineca-synthetic-datasets>

³⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/biochemistry-genetics-and-molecular-biology/expression-quantitative-trait-loci>

³¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7464116>

³² <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/rnaseq>

³³ <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/qcnorm>

³⁴ <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/genimpute/>

³⁵ <https://github.com/eQTL-Catalogue/qtimap/>

- trans-eQTL association testing: eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations³⁶
- trans-eQTL meta-analysis: eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis³⁷

Federated healthcare applications

The final aim of any biomedical research is to generate actionable results that can be used for the development of federated healthcare applications. For this purpose, CINECA WP5 has developed different tools to support clinicians estimate disease progression based on patient biomarkers, identify pathological variants, and assess their pathogenicity and propose treatments based on scientific literature.

- Federated Biomarker Discovery service

A service has been developed to evaluate genomic and transcriptomic features as biomarkers of disease progression and patient stratification³⁸. To assure reproducibility of the analysis results, Galaxy³⁹, a FAIR and user-friendly web-based data analysis platform, has been used as the workflow application for this service. A use case to analyse data from EGA was developed⁴⁰, which allowed for data access, download and analysis using the secure Galaxy environment using GA4GH standards and open-source tools like HTSget⁴¹, PyEGA3⁴² or Beacon⁴³. This workflow is publicly available⁴⁴ and can be used in the Galaxy environment by any user, which assures the reproducibility of the workflow results.

- FAIR Compliant Diagnostic Services

Another service has been developed to identify pathological variants⁴⁵, which includes:

- An Analytical Sandbox, connected to the EGA as a use case, which enables researchers to remotely log in to perform analyses from anywhere in the world, being able process next-generation sequencing (NGS) data, starting from sequenced reads in FASTQ format and resulting in a list of prioritised variants that could explain a patient's phenotype. This workflow provides the infrastructure and brings genomic data analysis to researchers without access to HPC compute facilities.
- A Diagnostic Reporting Application (DRA), a FAIR-compliant reporting demonstrator designed to generate diagnostic reports based on genomic SNP variants. The DRA generates diagnostic reports by extracting likely pathogenic variants from VIP⁴⁶, a

³⁶ <https://github.com/eQTLGen/PerCohortDataPreparations>

³⁷ <https://github.com/eQTLGen/MetaAnalysis>

³⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/7925781>

³⁹ <https://usegalaxy.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/variant-analysis/tutorials/trio-analysis/tutorial.html>

⁴¹ <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article/35/1/119/5040320>

⁴² <https://ega-archive.org/download/downloader-quickguide-APIv3>

⁴³ <https://beacon-project.io/>

⁴⁴ <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/363>

⁴⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/7925804>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/molgenis/vip/releases/tag/v4.5.0>

system to prioritise genetic variants provided by VCF⁴⁷ files, and presenting them alongside variant-associated disease information from Disgenet⁴⁸. The system stores data according to FAIR principles, using controlled vocabularies and ontologies, and has undergone a FAIR Maturity Assessment.

- Curation-support application for care planning

WP5 has worked on a workflow⁴⁹ to help clinicians characterize and understand the pathogenicity of a variant, and list possible treatments based on the literature.

- Pathogenicity assessment: It is achieved by computing the frequency of the variants in the biomedical literature using Variomes API⁵⁰ and retrieving variant scores from Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor using Ensembl API⁵¹.
- Treatment recommendations: It estimates the frequency of occurrence of drug treatment in the scientific literature associated with the variant, by using the ATC⁵² and Drugbank⁵³ databases.

The full workflow has been created as a CINECA Demonstrator⁵⁴

ELSI framework

During the whole length of the CINECA project Ethical, Legal and Social Implications (ELSI) have been considered of vital importance. WP7 first studied and catalogued ELSI issues the CINECA project could be confronted with⁵⁵. Then, the work was focused on identifying and discussing the gaps in the different legislative or regulatory frameworks (Europe, Canada and Africa) and corresponding literature⁵⁶. Finally, WP7 provided recommendations so that institutions can address the challenges regarding reuse of health/genomic data in CINECA from the ELSI perspective, and in the light of Open Science and FAIR principles⁵⁷.

In addition, a Data Management Plan⁵⁸ was developed, which provided information on CINECA data description, processing, storage and quality control, codes of conduct or management responsibilities for the CINECA partners.

⁴⁷ <https://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/VCFv4.2.pdf>

⁴⁸ <https://www.disgenet.org/home/>

⁴⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7925825>

⁵⁰ <https://candy.hesge.ch/Variomes/>

⁵¹ <https://genomebiology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13059-016-0974-4>

⁵² https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-211-89836-9_64

⁵³ <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/46/D1/D1074/4602867>

⁵⁴ <https://denver.hesge.ch/cineca/demo/step6>

⁵⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/3943732>

⁵⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/4298450>

⁵⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/7267158>

⁵⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/3909577>

3.2.2 Project Impact

Statistics from training and dissemination

Dissemination and training have been key aspects of the CINECA project since its inception, as transfer of knowledge to the relevant stakeholders is what will make CINECA outputs relevant to the scientific community. WP6 has centralized these CINECA efforts, planning a set of actions involving analysis of the stakeholders' needs and expectations, training activities and dissemination of the CINECA knowledge through different communication channels:

- Stakeholder analysis

A Stakeholder analysis⁵⁹ was performed, which provided insight on the needs and requirements of the CINECA stakeholder community (with responses from Europe, Africa and Canada stakeholders); it defined CINECA Competency profile⁶⁰ with 17 competencies important for stakeholders, which are accessible through the EMBL-EBI Competency Hub⁶¹.

- Training activities

WP6 planned the general training types at the beginning of the project⁶², which focused on knowledge exchange activities (through a CINECA staff exchange program⁶³), which were afterwards affected due to the Covid-19 pandemic's travel limitations, and internal learning (through webinars⁶⁴). In addition, short training videos⁶⁵ and short technical reports⁶⁶ provided continuous insights and updates on the new CINECA developments. Moreover, all these training activities were delivered throughout the entirety of the project^{67,68}. Many in-person workshops were planned, but they were also affected by the Covid-19 pandemic's travel limitations. However, WP6 adapted to the exceptional circumstances, and was able to organize numerous virtual workshops. From the 16 workshops organized by CINECA 13 were conducted virtually, and 3 in-person, reaching a total of 5.000 participants from around the world⁶⁹.

- Learning Pathway

CINECA, led by WP6, developed a Learning Pathway for Federated Analysis⁷⁰, an end-to-end online self-paced course covering relevant CINECA outputs following the "Researcher

⁵⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7733981>

⁶⁰ <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/framework/cineca/1.0>

⁶¹ <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/>

⁶² <https://zenodo.org/record/3952621>

⁶³ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/cineca-staff-visit-program>

⁶⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wzRY4uYNtoo&list=PLD6bAdANKoMVfd0e0cqV7KZGHtjFus9Hv>

⁶⁵ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/short-videos>

⁶⁶ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/>

⁶⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/6223125>

⁶⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/5795482>

⁶⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7925741>

⁷⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/materials/cineca-federated-data-analysis/>

Journey”; it covers federated data discovery, access, harmonization and analysis, and integrates tools, standards and use cases resulting from the technical work packages, in addition to training on the ELSI standards.

Activity Type	Number of activities
Staff visits	3
Webinars	18
Training courses and Workshops	17
Short training videos	20
Learning Pathway	1
Total	59

Table 1. Summary of all the CINECA training activities.

- Website and social media

The CINECA website⁷¹ has been essential for effectively communicating the project’s goals and progress, providing direct access to project information (history, partners, related projects), work done (WP organization, governance, deliverables, synthetic cohorts), dissemination (webinars, short videos and reports, Learning Pathway), and impact (related publications). In addition, CINECA has been an active participant in social media, with regular updates in Twitter and Youtube accounts, which helped increase project engagement and visibility.

- Publications

CINECA partners have published 14 peer-reviewed articles that feature work linked to the CINECA project⁷². This is a testament to the impact the CINECA project has had, and the contribution it has provided to the scientific community.

⁷¹ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/>

⁷² <https://www.cineca-project.eu/publications>

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

In order to quantify the impact of the CINECA project, a number of KPIs were described at the beginning of the project for the different WPs. The results are shown in table 2.

WP	KPI	Result
1	Nº of Beacons deployed	15 Beacons deployed by ELIXIR (4 in CINECA project)
1	Nº of visits to the CINECA service registry ⁷³	115,851 visits
2	GA4GH Passport consuming relying services in ELIXIR/LS AAI available for CINECA users	243
3	CINECA Synthetic Datasets created	CINECA synthetic cohort Africa H3ABioNet CINECA synthetic cohort Europe CH SIB CINECA synthetic cohort Europe UK1 CINECA synthetic cohort NA Canada CHILD
4	Nº of users running the eQTL usecase workflows	28 stars 11 forks 500 views/month 20 clones/month
5	Nº of queries to variants pathogenicity estimation services	29 requests/month 12 users/month
5	Nº of queries to variant expansion services	150 requests/month, 15 users/month 14 requests/month (beacon) 5 users/month (beacon)
5	Nº of times the HTSget EGA Galaxy download client (European public Galaxy server ⁷⁴) has been used	2.255 times by 39 distinct users
5	FAIR Maturity Score (EBI FAIR+) ⁷⁵	Good score (100%) at Level 4 - "Cross-community level semantically-typed data" (currently working on Level 5 - "Enterprise level managed data assets")
6	Number of learning interventions delivered	59 (see table 1)
7	ELSI Publications	1
8	Nº of GA4GH standards developed/implemented	10

Table 2. KPIs for the CINECA project

⁷³ <https://service-registry-demo.ega-archive.org/>

⁷⁴ <https://usegalaxy.eu>

⁷⁵ <https://fairplus.github.io/Data-Maturity/>

3.3 Next steps

The objective of the CINECA project is to establish a federated cloud enabled infrastructure that enables researchers and clinicians to access and analyze cohort data from multiple jurisdictions. To accomplish this goal, we followed the steps a clinician/researcher would pursue to discover, access and analyze cohort data, which we describe as the 'Researcher Journey'. As a result, we have carefully examined the challenges and obstacles associated with each step of the process and focused on developing solutions to overcome them and improve the current federated data analysis technological landscape.

CINECA has developed multiple tools to address the issues each researcher/clinician would face when following the Researcher journey: WP1 (Federated Data Discovery) has successfully implemented the GA4GH standard Beacon for data discovery, collaborating in the creation of different CINECA cohort beacon endpoints, enhancing discoverability by implementing a query expansion service, and providing a portal which users can access to perform their federated discovery queries; WP2 (Federated Data Access) has been involved in the development of GA4GH standards used for improving data accessibility (e.g. GA4GH Passports and AAI), and have implemented a proof-of-concept federated data access between Canada and Europe; WP3 (Data Harmonization) has implemented harmonization workflows currently used in other projects like IHCC, and created Synthetic Datasets, essential for the development of tools and trainings; WP4 (Federated Data Analysis) has successfully developed workflows that can perform federated analyses in different infrastructures; WP5 (Federated Healthcare Applications) has produced healthcare applications that can ease the clinician's diagnosis of patients by using federated clinical data.

In addition, WP7 (ELSI Framework) has provided insights on the implications of processing federated sensitive data among different jurisdictions, regarding the legal basis for its processing, required safeguards and privacy implementations, and the necessary stakeholder engagement.

All the CINECA information is publicly available through open platforms (CINECA website, Zenodo, Youtube, Github...), in addition to the training materials such as videos, recorded workshops, blog posts, etc. organized by WP6 (Dissemination and Communication).

Therefore, we consider the CINECA project has provided valuable standards, tools, workflows, and training that can be leveraged by future initiatives, enabling them to build upon the existing framework, ultimately enhancing the capability to establish a robust and scalable federated data analysis cloud-enabled infrastructure.

4. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AAI	Authorization & Authentication Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
C3G	Canadian Centre for Computational Genomics
CSC	Center for Scientific Computing
DAC	Data Access Committee
DRA	Diagnostic Reporting Application
DUO	Data Use Ontology
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Implications
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GECKO	Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology
H3Africa	Human Heredity & Health in Africa
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
QTL	Quantitative Trait Loci
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

5. Delivery and schedule

On time delivery

6. Adjustments made

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7. Appendices

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